

Biodiversity Conservation Monitoring System Image Detection using TensorFlow

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Abstract— As we know, there are a lot of different types of animal exist in the forest. Some of them are rare animals that are protected by government. Technology can help people discover the condition of animal that is protected by the government. With the forest characteristic, Deep learning is a multilayer neural networks, a kind of machine learning based on pattern recognition from input data, it has a property of unsupervised features learning which mean it can learn a datasets that only contain with few labeled data than unlabeled data which is important in image recognition method. There are some of deep learning methods such as CNN, DBNs and auto-encoders. In this paper we using TensorFlow an open source library for numerical computation, specializing in machine learning developed by Google Brain. TensorFlow is library that used in deep learning methods it similar to convolutional neural networks (CNN). It methods using inception a huge image classification model with millions of parameters that can differentiate a large number of kinds images/poets, to classified and training image data layer by layer. We using TensorFlow as an architecture to image detection system for detection and recognize an endangered animal at way kambas animal conservation. This image detection system could help researchers detection and recognition one of endangered animal (Dicerorhinus sumatrensis) Sumatran rhino which population in the end of 2015 approximately 100 in the wild.

Keywords: Deep Learning, Neural Networks, Image Detection System, TensorFlow, Endangered Animal.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, there are so many research in development image processing technology in computer vision. technology of image processing development has already used in many segments for helping human daily activities to get information such as security system that could recognize pedestrian, to recognize a foreign words (google translate) or detection any object using camera. Monitoring and surveillance system in forest area is a system developed by implementing the achievement of technology and information to collect data and information in different ways^[1].

In Sumatra, the government commit to save the Sumatran rhino from the extinction, they put cameras in the jungle and collecting data in the wild life to help researchers. The current camera technology is enough to just capturing a picture

continuously but because the absences of network infrastructure in the conservation area the keeper have to go into the jungle to collecting data and change the batteries every month.

By developing the camera device with trap area using infrared sensor, it increase the ability to capturing picture or recording video from an object that crosses on area. The data from camera will transmitted to raspberry and process it to collecting a picture that contain an object. For data transmission it uses UAV with Delay Tolerant Network architecture. It may help solve researcher's problem to collecting data. DTN architecture use store-carry and forward concept, which mean when collecting the data and the connection not available, DTN will carry the message until the connection available and the data fully transmitted and sent to the computer center.

After collecting data and put it into computer center, we can detection and recognize the image using TensorFlow library. TensorFlow have been trained the rhino data to make the detection works, the rhino data was trained and classified with inception, to make the machine learning acknowledge if that data is rhino.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Tensor

TensorFlow in generally is deep learning library, deep learning is kind of machine learning method which can learn from datasets with few labeled data and many unlabeled data, which is important in image recognition method, deep learning features will extracting input that we gave and learn layer by layer, the output of one layer is the input of the next layer^[4].

Figure 1 TensorFlow Deep Neural Networks Layers.

TensorFlow is represented by nodes and edges, nodes represent mathematical operations and edges represent multidimensional data arrays (tensor) to be communicated between nodes^{[1][10]}.

Figure 2 TensorFlow Data Flow Diagram^[10].

B. Convolutional Neural Networks.

CNN architecture is kind of deep learning method for image classification tasks. Before image used for classification, CNN apply a series to filters a raw pixel data of an image extract and

learn higher-level features then we can use the data for classification. Simple model of CNN can you see in figure 3.

Figure 3 TensorFlow Data Flow Diagram^[7].

CNN contain three components such as ;

- Convolutional layers, which apply specified number of convolution filters to image.
- Pooling layers, which down sample image data extracted then to reduce the dimensionality to decrease time
- Dense layer, which perform classification.

C. Inception Module

To training our data we use inception V3, the main idea of inception is how convolutional vision networks could be approximated and covered an optimal local sparse structure by readily available dense component^[3].

Figure 4 Full Inception Module^[3].

The first phase is analyze all the images on disk and calculates the bottleneck, inception is made by many layer these layers are pre-trained and already very valuable at finding summarizing information to help classify most image.

The bottom box is an input and the top is output, and the rest of box basically is a layer of convolutional networks, which could choice of operation, pooling operation, convolutional operation or filter size. What an Inception module allows you to do is perform all of these operations in parallel^[3].

D. Transfer Learning..

In this paper we using transfer learning in TensorFlow. Without amount of data from google, we cant possibly to create effective deep learning model. Transfer learning is the process of taking a pre-trained model, which means we utilizing a model that has been trained on another problem and retraining the data in similar problem, we just utilizing the final layer of the network and replace it with our classifier it make training the data done in short order^[10].

E. Comparing Image Detection System.

Comparing to other image detection system such as deformable part model and YOLO.

- a. DPM is algorithm is image detection architecture which use a sliding window approach to object detection, this model trained using discriminative procedure that require bounding boxes the object in set of images. To accurate result and more efficient we could use the PASCAL VOC benchmarks and INRIA person data set^[6]. DPM was an innovation model from Dalal-Triggs that used HOG. In model pyramid it will separate the object into some part and classified them, which mean DPM also can have high probability on detecting object but it complicated to train the data.
- b. YOLO model is a Convolutional Networks (ConvNets) with unified detection, basically YOLO also part of deep learning, which can detect multiple objects in an image simultaneously by dividing the image into a SxS grid and each grid will predict bounding boxes of object, confidence score and class probabilities. the confidence will reflect the score that box contain the images and think how accurate that box detect the image^{[5][8]}.

III. DESIGN

To develop image detection using TensorFlow we use python in Docker a virtual machine to run and compile TensorFlow. Table 4.

Table 1 Experimantal Environment.

Software environment	Hardware environment
Operating System :	Computer : Asus N46V
Windows 10 64 bit.	CPU: Intel Core i5
Development tools:	Memory : 4GB
Docker virtual machine	Grafik : Nvidia GEFORCE 650
TensorFlow+pyhton	

The whole system that we build could seen in figure 5,

1. Sensor detection an object.
2. Trigger an Android to capture picture.
3. Raspberry Pi acts as a bundle receiver from Andoid.
4. Raspberry sent file to UAV.
5. Computer center get the data and detect an object.

Figure 5 Block Diagram.

That diagram show us how the system works, when there are animal crosses the sensor are it will trigger the trap camera to capture a picture or record a video using Android smartphone. After that the android smartphone would send image and video using DTN to raspberry pi, and detecting an object or not.

For image files detection in raspberry, there are 2 image pre-processing method that are used., Gaussian-Blur method and converting RGB to HSV color space. It will acknowledge the picture only and try to detect if the picture contains an animal or not, if the picture is containing an animal it will separate into another folder and will collected by UAV.

Sending image file into UAV also using DTN, when connection available UAV will start collecting data, and if the connection is not available UAV will carry the file until the connection available and continue collecting data. When data move to computer in data center it will using image detection system using TensorFlow to detect an images that contains only a rhino and separating it with other image.

IV. RESULT AND CONCLUSION

TensorFlow that used in this research works fine, as the result that we get TensorFlow can detect an object from approximately 20 images in short amount of time. The simulation was set to detect a rhino that contain in every image from any angle and position also mixed with some other image beside the rhino. The simulation successfully detected a rhino and spilt them into different location.

As the result TensorFlow detected accuracy approximately about 95%, but there is condition that image was detected contain other animal, it because the unique of the rhino such as the body, legs or another part has similarities with some animal or in that picture contain a rhino and other object but its still detecting as a rhino.

Table 1 Result of Whole Program Test.

No	File's Name	Percentage	Rhino detected	Rhino undetected
1	01.sumatran rhino.jpg	63%	Yes	
2	1.jpg	87%	Yes	
3	Clouded leopard.jpg	0.8%		No
4	Malayan sunbear.jpg	1%		No

5	3.jpg	94%	yes	
6	Sumatran tiger.jpg	2%		No
7	Malayan tapir.jpg	55%	Yes	
8	7.jpg	96%	Yes	
9	8.jpg	96%	Yes	
10	Sumatran elephant.jpg	2%		No
11	12.jpg	92%	Yes	
12	17.jpg	95%	Yes	
13	Rhino.jpg	86%	Yes	
14	Forest.jpg	8%		No
15	Lasndscape.jpg	9%		No
16	Human.jpg	50%	Yes	
17	People.jpg	0.5%		No
18	forest.jpg	8%		No
19	Muncak deer.jpg	1%		No
20	Sambar deer.jpg	43%		No

The purpose of this research is to apply the machine learning architecture to build image detection and recognition system for detect a rhino in the wild. The system can separate the picture that is contain a rhino or not. Based on several tests even though [the program could detect the object with approximately 95% accurate, there is also have some mistaken to recognize the object.

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